

Sección B: Partner responsible for the plan

This section includes the information of the Partner responsible for the plan

B1. Name of the partner responsible for the plan

Indicate the full name of the Partner responsible for the plan

B2. Partner website

Include, if you have, like this: www.name.eu

If it is not located from, it must indicate: not available

B3. Country of the partner responsible for the plan

In English

Sección C: Plan analysis

In this section a detailed analysis of the plan is made

C1. Does the plan have an executive summary?

Sí
No

C2. What elements does the executive summary contain?

Select the ones that correspond. Indicate, when necessary, the details of the element

Purpose
Scope
Structure
Others

C3. Does the plan have a project overview?

Sí
No

C4. What elements does the project overview contain?

Select the ones that correspond. Indicate, when necessary, the details of the element

Important Facts
Key Numbers
List of partners
Goals of project
Vision of project

Expected results of the project

Infographics, photos or explanatory graphics

Others

C5. Does the plan have a section with objectives of the dissemination strategy?

Si

No

C6. What elements does the objectives of the dissemination strategy contain?

Select the ones that correspond. Indicate, when necessary, the details of the element

Set up the information dissemination mechanisms and strategies

Create a community composed by the project partners and interested stakeholders

Perform targeted communication activities for different stakeholders

Carry out dissemination activities to raise international awareness and interest in project activities and achieved results

Contribute the relevant project results to the corresponding stakeholders

Conduct liaison with other EU, regional and national projects to maximise the impact

Others

Sección D: Strategy

Communication and Dissemination Strategy

D1. Does the plan define both a internal and external dissemination strategy?

Internal and external

Only external

Only internal

D2. What elements does the goals of the external dissemination strategy contain?

Select the ones that correspond. Indicate, when necessary, the details of the element

It does not declare them

Prepare strategy and plan of dissemination activities

Create a corporative image of the project

Establish, update and maintain the project website

Use social networking tools

Prepare video release

Participate in events

Others

Sección E: Targeted Audiences

E1. In the definition of audience use the model of the quadruple helix?

The quadruple helix stimate that it's necessary that the communication reaches at government, industry, academia, and civil participants, including Media, to bring a multidisciplinary viewpoints that promotes teamwork, collaboration and the sharing of ideas.

Si

No

E2. What are primary communication targets?

Select the ones that correspond. Indicate, when necessary, the details of the element

Research initiatives covering synergistic subject matter

System developers, who constitute the route-to-market for the technology aspects of project

Consultores de negocios que puedan trabajar con resultados tempranos.

Organisations that set standards in the subject matter fields

Research communities in areas of direct, specific relevance to the project

Wider research community in areas related to our project activities

National, regional and European funding bodies

Policy makers at European or national level

Bodies involved in vocational training and worker development

Vendors, integrators and sector organisations of industrial

Sector or geographical organisations of industrial end users

Mass Media

Social Media. Influencers

Specialized journalists

Citizens science

General Public

Schools and students

Others

E3. What are secondary communication targets?

Select the ones that correspond. Indicate, when necessary, the details of the element

Research initiatives covering synergistic subject matter

System developers, who constitute the route-to-market for the technology aspects of project

Consultores de negocios que puedan trabajar con resultados tempranos.

Organisations that set standards in the subject matter fields

Research communities in areas of direct, specific relevance to the project

Wider research community in areas related to our project activities

National, regional and European funding bodies

Policy makers at European or national level

Bodies involved in vocational training and worker development

Vendors, integrators and sector organisations of industrial

Sector or geographical organisations of industrial end users

- Mass Media
- Social Media. Influencers
- Specialized journalists
- Citizens science
- General Public
- Schools and students
- Others

Sección F: Dissemination Tools

F1. What tools does the plan propose?

Indicate all those that are indicated in the plan.

- Project corporative Image
- Digital Channels
- Promotional printed material
- Work with media
- Events and networking
- Promotional merchandise (goodies)
- Others
- Otro

Otro

F2. Select the specific tools of Project corporative Image

- Graphic identity
- Branding
- Project Templates
- Others

F3. Select the specific tools of Digital Channels

- Public Website
- Private online portal
- Social Media
- Newsletter
- Others

F4. Select the specific tools of Promotional printed material

- Flyer
- Brochure
- Fatsheet

Poster

Others

F5. Select the specific tools to Work with Media

Kit media

Video release

Press Releases

Data Base of journalists

Sending to contacts included in Media database

Adaptation of content to create a story on the project website

Others

F6. Select the specific tools to Events and networking

Congress

Exhibitions

Workshop

Interaction with other projects

Training activities

Feedback Questionnaires

Others

F7. Indicate what specific tools to Promotional merchandise (goodies)

Sección G: Monitoring Tools

Tools and methods to following and measure the impact of the different instruments of communication

G1. What tools does the project establish to measure the results of the communication and dissemination plan?

Indicate all those that are indicated in the plan.

Web site tracking

Number of scientific articles selected in major conferences and journals

References to the project in other projects, research, studies, etc.

Number of news items or take up of news items in external channels

Others

G2. Describes tools and KPIs to measure communication results

Sección H: Final general description

Include a final general description or aspects that are not included in the previous questions and that are relevant

H1. Final description

Include a final general description or aspects that are not included in the previous questions and that are relevant

ANALYSIS VARIABLES

Model MAPEDR

Below are the variables used in the analysis model indicating the nature, type, values that can be taken and the definition of the variable.

Variable	Cl/CT ¹	N/I/O/D/C ²	Values	Definition
Project duration (months)	Quantitative	Continuous	Number of months of the Project	Amount of time, in months, that has been established for the realization of the project.
Country in which it was carried out	Qualitative	Discrete	English Country Name	Country of the entity leading the project.
Summary	Qualitative	Nominal	Yes, No, N/A	Summary of the communication plan. Aggregated variable.
Purpose	Qualitative	Nominal	Yes, No, N/A	Statement of the purpose of the PEDR
Scope	Qualitative	Nominal	Yes, No, N/A	Definition of the target audience
Structure	Qualitative	Nominal	Yes, No, N/A	Statement on project structure
Project overview	Qualitative	Nominal	Yes, No, N/A	General summary of the project and the PRDP. Aggregated variable.
Important facts	Qualitative	Nominal	Yes, No, N/A	These are important data exposed at the beginning of the project
Key Numbers	Quantitative	Discreta	Yes, No, N/A	Important figures
List of partners	Qualitative	Nominal	Yes, No, N/A	Name of the project partners.
Goals of project	Qualitative	Nominal	Yes, No, N/A	Goals to be achieved.
Project vision	Qualitative	Nominal	Yes, No, N/A	General approach to the Project
Expected results	Qualitative	Nominal	Yes, No, N/A	Results to be achieved
Infographics, photos and explanatory graphics	Qualitative	Ordinal	Yes, No, N/A	Graphic documents used
Section with objectives of the dissemination strategy	Qualitative	Ordinal	Yes, No, N/A	Information on the project's dissemination strategies.
Establish information dissemination mechanisms and strategies	Qualitative	Ordinal	Yes, No, N/A	Approach to how information is to be disseminated.
Create a community composed of project partners and stakeholders	Qualitative	Nominal	Yes, No, N/A	Exclusive community for project partners
Carry out specific communication activities for different stakeholders	Qualitative	Nominal	Yes, No, N/A	Individual communication for stakeholders and partners.
Carry out dissemination activities to increase international awareness and interest in the project's activities and results.	Qualitative	Nominal	Yes, No, N/A	Activities created in order to increase the dissemination of the Project
Contribute the relevant project results to the relevant stakeholders	Qualitative	Nominal	Yes, No, N/A	Share project results with partners and other stakeholders

¹ Qualitative o Quantitative

² Nominal (Quantitative), Range, Ordinal, Discreet or Continued (Quantitative)

Liaise with other EU, regional and national projects to maximise impact	Qualitative	Nominal	Yes, No, N/A	Create connections with other projects to increase dissemination and impact
Internal communication	Qualitative	Nominal	Yes, No, N/A	Communication that exists within the project itself with respect to project workers
External communication	Qualitative	Nominal	Yes, No, N/A	Specific communication for the people targeted by the project such as through social networks
Using the quadruple helix	Qualitative	Nominal	Yes, No, N/A	It promotes teamwork, participation and exchange of ideas through four axes: academia, public administration, business and people.
Primary Communication Goals	Qualitative	Nominal	Yes, No, N/A	Main objectives of the plan
Research initiatives covering synergistic topics	Qualitative	Nominal	Yes, No, N/A	It is a matter of developing a joint action of several bodies
System developers, who constitute the route to market for the technological aspects of the project	Qualitative	Nominal	Yes, No, N/A	It serves to bring the technological aspects of the plan to the market
Business consultants who can work with early results	Qualitative	Nominal	Yes, No, N/A	Estimated results are established before the finals
Organizations that set standards in the thematic areas.	Qualitative	Nominal	Yes, No, N/A	A standard model of the thematic fields is established
Investigate communities in areas of direct and specific relevance to the project	Qualitative	Nominal	Yes, No, N/A	Investigation of the areas most important to the plan
Wider research community in areas related to our project activities	Qualitative	Nominal	Yes, No, N/A	The areas of importance in relation to the project are further investigated
National, regional and European funding agencies	Qualitative	Nominal	Yes, No, N/A	Agencies acting on the plan
Policy makers at European or national level.	Qualitative	Nominal	Yes, No, N/A	Responsible parties acting on the plan
Organisations involved in the professional training and development of workers.	Qualitative	Nominal	Yes, No, N/A	Agency employed in the development of workers
Vendors, integrators and industry sector organizations.	Qualitative	Nominal	Yes, No, N/A	Actions aimed at commercials from the industry
Sectoral or geographical organisations of industrial end users.	Qualitative	Nominal	Yes, No, N/A	Organization of area used for industrial purposes
Mass media	Qualitative	Nominal	Yes, No, N/A	Actions aimed at the mass media
Social media	Qualitative	Nominal	Yes, No, N/A	Actions aimed at social networks. (Facebook, instagram, Twiter, etc.)
Specialized journalists	Qualitative	Nominal	Yes, No, N/A	Journalism professionals specialized in the topic being worked on.
Citizen science	Qualitative	Nominal	Yes, No, N/A	Scientific research carried out by a group of collaborators, in whole or in part by scientists and professionals together with ordinary people.
Generic audience	Qualitative	Nominal	Yes, No, N/A	General public
Schools and students	Qualitative	Nominal	Yes, No, N/A	Students from educational centres

Secondary communication objectives	Qualitative	Nominal	Yes, No, N/A	Secondary objectives of the plan
Tools proposed in the plan	Qualitative	Nominal	Yes, No, N/A	Series of elements that the plan provides for its dissemination
Project's corporate image	Qualitative	Nominal	Yes, No, N/A	Tool for the communication plan that consists of creating an image that identifies you
Graphical identity	Qualitative	Nominal	Yes, No, N/A	Difference from other plans
Brand	Qualitative	Nominal	Yes, No, N/A	It allows to identify or distinguish
Digital Channels	Qualitative	Nominal	Yes, No, N/A	Includes websites, social networks, newsletters, etc.
Public website	Qualitative	Nominal	Yes, No, N/A	Public project website for anyone to find out
Private online portal	Qualitative	Nominal	Yes, No, N/A	Web space reserved for project partners and stakeholders
Social networks	Qualitative	Nominal	Yes, No, N/A	Creation of project profiles in different social networks in order to reach more people
Newsletters	Qualitative	Nominal	Yes, No, N/A	Informative digital publication that is distributed through e-mail with certain periodicity.
Promotional printed material	Qualitative	Nominal	Yes, No, N/A	Advertising material to promote the Project
Flyer	Qualitative	Nominal	Yes, No, N/A	Medium-sized graphic advertising
Brochure	Qualitative	Nominal	Yes, No, N/A	Printed format between 4 and 40 pages
Fact sheet	Qualitative	Nominal	Yes, No, N/A	Fact sheet highlighting the most important or key points
Poster	Qualitative	Nominal	Yes, No, N/A	Poster ready to be hung on the wall as an informative element
Working with the media	Qualitative	Nominal	Yes, No, N/A	Presence in the media
Video release	Qualitative	Nominal	Yes, No, N/A	Audiovisual content creation
Press release	Qualitative	Nominal	Yes, No, N/A	Preparation of press releases
Database of journalists	Qualitative	Nominal	Yes, No, N/A	Database to contact specialized journalists
Events and networks	Qualitative	Nominal	Yes, No, N/A	Events which project representatives attend, e.g. to give lectures, interact with other projects, etc.
Conferences	Qualitative	Nominal	Yes, No, N/A	A meeting of people from different places who share a profession, and conferences or exhibitions related to their work are presented.
Exhibitions	Qualitative	Nominal	Yes, No, N/A	Meetings presenting the results of the project

Workshop	Qualitative	Nominal	Yes, No, N/A	Workshop to bring the results of the new knowledge acquired by the project closer
Interacting with other projects	Qualitative	Nominal	Yes, No, N/A	Employed to exchange information and have a different view of one's project.
Training activities	Qualitative	Nominal	Yes, No, N/A	Activity to teach about project issues
Feedback questionnaires	Qualitative	Nominal	Yes, No, N/A	Questionnaire to find out how you score on the communication plan
Merchandising promocional	Qualitative	Nominal	Yes, No, N/A	Advertising products to publicize the project.
Results of the communication and dissemination plan	Qualitative	Nominal	Yes, No, N/A	Measurement of the communication and dissemination results of the Project
Website monitoring	Qualitative	Continua	Yes, No, N/A	Number of interactions that the project website has
Number of selected scientific articles in major conferences and journals.	Qualitative	Discreta	Yes, No, N/A	Results of the plan through how many articles about it have been included in conferences and journals
References to the project in other projects, research, studies, etc.	Qualitative	Discreta	Yes, No, N/A	Obtaining results depending on whether the communication plan has been referred to in other projects or research
Number of news or news captures on external channels.	Qualitative	Discrete	Yes, No, N/A	Data collection according to the number of news items about the plan